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Studies on Diphenyl Sulphones. Preparation and Antimicrobial Activity of *p,p'*-Bis(2-aryl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-5-yl)diphenyl Sulphones and *p,p'*-Bis(3-chloro-4-aryl-2-azetidinon-1-ylaminocarbonyl)-diphenylsulphones

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SOME 2,5-disubstituted-1,3,4-oxadiazole derivatives possess wide spectrum of biological properties¹. Several new such derivatives (4) have been synthesised with a view to obtaining better therapeutic agents. A large number of antibiotics contain β -lactam heterocyclic moiety². Sulphones are reported to possess important therapeutic properties³. We have combined the two structures and synthesised some new 2-azetidinone derivatives.

p,p'-Dicarboxydiphenyl sulphone (1) was esterified with absolute ethanol and subsequently condensed with hydrazine hydrate to get *p,p'*-dihydrazinocarbonyldiphenyl sulphone (3). The hydrazide (3) on condensation with different aromatic acids in presence of phosphorous oxychloride gave (Scheme 1) the *p,p'*-bis(2-aryl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-5-yl)-diphenyl sulphones (4). The hydrazide (3) on condensation with different aromatic aldehydes gave the Schiff base (5), which on treatment with chloroacetyl chloride in presence of triethylamine gave *p,p'*-bis(3-chloro-4-aryl-2-azetidinon-1-ylaminocarbonyl)diphenylsulphones (6). The compounds were screened for their antimicrobial activity.

The antimicrobial screening of the oxadiazole and 2-azetidinone derivatives was carried out using cup-plate method⁴ at a concentration of 50 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *S. citrus*, *Pseudomonas fluores*, *Escherichia coli* and fungi *Aspergillus flavus* and *Candida albicans*.

The 1,3,4-oxadiazole derivatives (3) showed good activity against *P. fluores* and *C. albicans*, and moderately active against *S. aureus*, *E. coli*, *S. citrus* and *A. flavus*. The maximum activity was observed in the derivatives when R=2- and 3-aminophenyl against *P. fluores*, and R=3-chlorophenyl and 2-hydroxy-3-naphthyl against *C. albicans*.

Most of the 2-azetidinone derivatives (6) were moderately active against different strains of bacteria and fungi. The maximum activity was observed in the derivatives when R=4-chlorophenyl, 2,4-dichlorophenyl, and 4-hydroxyphenyl against *P. fluores*, and when R=2- and 4-methoxyphenyl against *C. albicans*.

Experimental

Mps. were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. The structures of the compounds were established on the basis of their elemental analysis and spectral data. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu IR-435 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra on a XL-100A (100.1 MHz) spectrometer using TMS as internal reference.

p,p'-Dicarboxydiphenyl sulphone (2): A mixture of *p,p'*-dicarboxydiphenyl sulphone (61.2 g, 0.2 mol), absolute ethanol (200 ml) and sulphuric acid (5.4 ml) was refluxed for 5 h. The excess ethanol was then distilled off and the residue poured onto crushed ice. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol, (47.1 g, 65%), m.p. 159° (Found: S, 8.3. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_6\text{S}$ requires: S, 8.4%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1 150 and 1 330 cm^{-1} (S=O asym. and sym.), 1 725 (C=O), 2 940 (CH_2 sym) and 2 920 cm^{-1} (CH_2 sym.); δ (DMSO- d_6) 1.3 (6H, t, $\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 4.4 (4H, q, $\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$) and 8.1 (8H, m, ArH).

p,p'-Dihydrazinocarbonyl diphenylsulphone (3): An aqueous solution of hydrazine hydrate (10 ml; 80%) was added to a suspension of 2 (6.7 g, 0.02 mol) in ethanol (30 ml). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 6 h, then cooled to room temperature and poured in ice-water. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol, (4.2 g, 68%), m.p. 248° (Found: N, 16.71. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_4\text{O}_4\text{S}$ requires: N, 16.77%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1 155 and 1 290 cm^{-1} (S=O asym. and sym.), 1 660 (C=O) and 3 300 cm^{-1} (NH or NH_2); δ (DMSO- d_6) 4.6 (4H, s, NHNH_2), 8.2–7.5 (8H, m, ArH) and 10.02 (2H, s, CONH).

p,p'-Bis(2-aryl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-5-yl)diphenylsulphone (4): A mixture of 3 (3.34 g, 0.01 mol), benzoic acid (2.44 g, 0.02 mol) and phosphorous

Scheme 1

oxychloride (5 ml) was refluxed for 6 h. The resulting solid was crystallised from dioxane-DMF (3 : 1) solvent, (3.6 g, 71%), m.p. 180° (Found : N, 11.0. C₂₈H₁₈O₄S₄ requires : N, 11.06%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1 155 and 1 320 (S=O asym. and sym.), 1 105, 1 670 cm⁻¹ (=C-O-C= and C=N respectively of oxadiazole moiety); δ (DMSO-d₆) 7.1-8.3 (18H, m, ArH).

TABLE 1 - PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 4*

Sl. no.	R	M.p. °C	Yield %
1.	Phenyl	180	70
2.	3-Tolyl	276	68
3.	4-Tolyl	281	71
4.	2-Chlorophenyl	130	82
5.	3-Chlorophenyl	141	88
6.	4-Chlorophenyl	167	67
7.	2-Aminophenyl	112	81
8.	3-Aminophenyl	178	72
9.	4-Aminophenyl	180	78
10.	2-Nitrophenyl	131	60
11.	3-Nitrophenyl	240	67
12.	4-Nitrophenyl	205	81
13.	2-Hydroxyphenyl	255	71
14.	3-Hydroxyphenyl	215	82
15.	4-Hydroxyphenyl	281	75
16.	2,4-Dihydroxyphenyl	201	72
17.	2,6-Dihydroxyphenyl	227	61
18.	3,5-Dihydroxyphenyl	253	63
19.	1-Hydroxy-2-naphthyl	171	74
20.	2-Hydroxy-3-naphthyl	218	71
21.	2-Methoxyphenyl	172	80
22.	2,3-Dimethoxyphenyl	152	88
23.	4-Bromophenyl	181	80
24.	3-Pyridyl	257	67

*All the compounds gave satisfactory N analysis.

Similarly, other aromatic acids were condensed (Table 1).

***p,p'*-Bis(benzaldehydrazinocarbonyl)diphenylsulphone (5):** A mixture of benzaldehyde (2.02 ml, 0.02 mol) and *p,p'*-bis(hydrazinocarbonyl)diphenylsulphone (3.34 g, 0.01 mol) in ethanol was refluxed for 6 h. The reaction mixture was then poured over crushed ice and the resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol, (5.0 g, 98%), m.p. 81° (Found : N, 10.9. C₂₈H₂₂N₄O₄S requires : N, 10.98%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1 140 and 1 300 (S=O asym and sym. respectively), 3 250 (NH) and 1 600 cm⁻¹ (N=C); δ (DMSO-d₆) 7.0-8.1 (18H, m, ArH), 8.62 (2H, s, CH=NH) and 8.4 (10.92) (2H, s, NH-CO-[N=O(OH)-]).

Similarly, other anils were prepared.

***p,p'*-Bis(3-chloro-4-aryl-2-azetidinon-1-ylaminocarbonyl)diphenylsulphone (6):** To, *p,p'*-bis(benzaldehydrazinocarbonyl)diphenylsulphone (2.55 g, 0.005 mol) in dry benzene (50 ml), chloroacetyl chloride (0.79 ml, 0.1 mol) was added slowly at room temperature with constant stirring. The reaction mixture was then stirred for 8 h after adding triethylamine (1.39 ml, 0.01 mol) and left for 3 days. The excess solvent was then distilled off and the contents were poured into ice-water. The resulting solid was crystallised from dioxane-DMF (3 : 1), (2.3 g, 69%), m.p. 210° (Found : N, 8.82. C₃₂H₂₄Cl₂N₄O₆S requires : N, 8.45%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1 120 and 1 310 (S=O asym. and sym. respectively), 3 350 (NH), 1 650 and 1 705 cm⁻¹ (C=O aliphatic and β -lactam respectively).

Similarly, other 2-azetidiones were prepared (Table 2).

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 6*

Sl. no.	R	M.p. °C	Yield %
1.	Phenyl	210	68
2.	4-Tolyl	192	52
3.	2-Chlorophenyl	259	70
4.	4-Chlorophenyl	248	72
5.	2,4-Dichlorophenyl	271	60
6.	2,6-Dichlorophenyl	238	68
7.	2-Methoxyphenyl	278	71
8.	4-Methoxyphenyl	213	61
9.	3,4-Dimethoxyphenyl	251	58
10.	3-Methoxy-2-hydroxyphenyl	178	60
11.	3-Methoxy-4-hydroxyphenyl	185	52
12.	2-Nitrophenyl	217	67
13.	3-Nitrophenyl	243	60
14.	2-Hydroxyphenyl	256	62
15.	3-Hydroxyphenyl	158	78

*All the compounds gave satisfactory N analysis.

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Synthesis of 3-(p diazobenzoyl Nβ-arylidinohydrazone)indoles

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3-SUBSTITUTED-indoles are well-known for their pharmacological and biochemical activities¹. Hydrazone derivatives find considerable use in chemotherapy, mostly as antitubercular agents². Since the use of isonicotinic acid hydrazide (INH)

as a clinically effective antitubercular drug, a large number of acid hydrazides and their condensation derivatives have been prepared and tested for antitubercular properties. They have also been found to possess various biological activities³.

Keeping this in view, we have studied the synthesis (Scheme 1) and antimicrobial activities of some 3-(p-diazobenzoyl-Nβ-arylidinohydrazone)-indoles. The structure of the compounds have

been established on the basis of their elemental analyses, m.m.p. and ir spectral data. The ir spectra of the compounds show characteristic bands at 3 420 (NH), 1 500 and 1 530 (C-H and C-C stretching and deformation vibration of indole heterocycle), 1 665 (C=N), 1 575 (N=N), 1 620 (NHCO) and 840 cm^{-1} (1,4-disubstituted benzene).

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. The purity of the compounds was checked by tlc. The ir spectra (KBr) of the compounds were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer.

p-Aminobenzoyl-Nβ-arylidinohydrazines (2)⁴: A mixture of *p*-aminobenzoylhydrazide (1) and appropriate aldehyde in ethanol was kept at room